

Notes

Mannich Bases derived from 4-Naphthyl Thiazoles

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A great deal of interest has recently focussed around the synthesis of amino methyl derivatives because of their potential usefulness either as anti-spasmodics or antihistaminics.¹⁻⁴ "Sestron"¹, an amino alkyl compound, was first used as a cure for

were prepared by the condensation of their respective ω -bromo aceto naphthenes with thiourea in alcoholic solution according to the procedure described by Rout *et al.*⁵. The amino methyl derivatives were prepared by the condensation of the above amino compounds with para formaldehyde and various keto methylene compounds viz., acetophenone pyrazolone, dinitro phenyl pyrazolone, and rhodanine according to our previous procedure². Amino methyl compounds V and VIII, however, separated as oils, which presented difficulty in crystallisation. However, they underwent solidification by repeated boiling with water. The different Mannich bases prepared have been listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound No.	Nature of ϕ_1	Nature of A	Yield %	M.P. °C	Formula	% of Nitrogen	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	α -naphthyl	acetophenone	47	87	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	7.68	7.82
2.	-do-	pyrazolone	50	98	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	13.21	13.34
3.	-do-	dinitro phenyl pyrazolone	45	99	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₅ S	14.62	14.73
4.	-do-	rhodanine	50	80	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₃ O	9.50	9.68
5.	β -naphthyl	acetophenone	60	85	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	7.59	7.82
6.	-do-	pyrazolone	50	103	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	13.03	13.34
7.	-do-	dinitro phenyl pyrazolone	50	110	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₅ S	14.69	14.73
8.	-do-	rhodanine	45	133	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₃ O	9.46	9.68

renal spasm and since that time a large number of compounds have been reported in the chemical literature. In the present communication eight new amino methyl derivatives derived from the condensation of 2-amino 4-alpha and beta naphthyl thiazoles with para formaldehyde and various keto methylene compounds have been reported and these compounds are being screened for their spasmolytic activities.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

2-amino 4-alpha naphthyl thiazole, m.p. 144° and 2-amino 4-beta naphthyl thiazole, m.p. 151°

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